

Chemical Constituents of *Eucalyptus* hybrid

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EUCALYPTUS hybrid (Mysore gum, mainly *E. tereticornis*¹) is extensively grown in India under the social forestry programme. From the acetone extract of its leaves, ursolic acid, ursolic acid lactone and 2- α -hydroxyursolic acid were reported earlier². Ursolic acid possesses medicinal properties³. The results of chemical examination of the polar fraction of an extract of the leaves and wood of this plant are reported in this paper.

The shade-dried powdered leaves (395 g; collected from FRI campus) and wood (490 g; from Yamuna Nagar, Haryana) were successively extracted separately with petroleum ether, acetone and alcohol. The alcoholic extract of the leaves was suspended in H₂O (500 ml) and extracted successively with EtOAc and n-butanol. Column chromatography of the n-butanol fraction (15 g) over silica gel afforded two compounds A and B.

Compound A, obtained on elution with EtOAc-C₆H₆ (8 : 2), was crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃ (400 mg), m.p. 235–40°d; ir and pmr (methyl ester) spectra were identical to those of authentic gallic acid.

Elution with EtOAc-C₆H₆ (9 : 1) furnished compound B, which was crystallised from MeOH as white solid (220 mg), m.p. 221–22°, [α]_D²⁰ –55° (c, 0.08 in pyridine), and gave a positive Molisch's test and brown ferric reaction. Its aqueous solution when poured over pellets of KOH and left undisturbed for some time gave violet colour characteristic of 2-methyl chromones⁴; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400br, 1 660, 1 620, 1 590, 1 560, 1 440, 1 415, 1 370, 1 340, 1 300, 1 260, 1 200, 1 170, 1 115, 1 090, 1 035, 1 005, 930, 900, 860 and 825 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 230, 248, 258, 288, 312; +NaOAc 225, 248, 288, 312; +AlCl₃ 260, 303, 366; +AlCl₃+HCl 260, 304, 368; +NaOMe 220, 268, 361 nm; pmr δ (90 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 2.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.18–3.60 (6H, m, sugar protons), 4.93 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, H-1'), 6.12 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.32 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 6-H), 6.52 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H). Acid hydrolysis gave an aglycone, m.p. 268–70°, which was identified as 2-methyl-5,7-dihydroxychromone⁵ (ir, uv, pmr of methyl ether and mass spectrum of glycoside acetate⁶) and glucose (tlc & pc). Uv spectra indicated glucose to be at 7-position. Acetylation with Ac₂O–C₆H₅N on a steam-bath for 5 h gave a penta-acetate, m.p. 130–32°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 750, 1 660, 1 620, 1 250, 1 220, 1 180, 1 170, 1 080, 1 050, 935, 900, 850 and 750 cm⁻¹; pmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl₃) 2.05 (9H, s, 3×Ac), 2.10 (3H, s, Ac), 2.30 (3H, s, Ac), 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-2), 3.97 (1H, b, 5'-H), 4.22 (2H, m, 6'-H, H), 4.92–5.35 (4H, m, sugar protons), 5.98 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.60 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H at C-6) and 6.86 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H at C-8); m/z 564 (M⁺, 56), 536 (12), 524 (98), 450 (5), 408 (12), 331 (98), 271 (63), 192 (100), 169 (98), 127 (76) and 109 (98). The above data led to the characterisation of compound B as 7- β -D-glucosyloxy-5-hydroxy-2-methylchromone⁷ which has not so far been reported from the genus *Eucalyptus*.

The petroleum ether extract of wood furnished on column chromatography β -sitosterol (50 mg), identified by m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra. The acetone extract of wood furnished gallic acid (250 mg), also characterised by m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra. The second compound from the acetone extract was characterised as (+)-catechin by its acetate, pmr, mass spectra and superimposable ir spectra.

These compounds were not reported earlier from *Eucalyptus* hybrid wood.

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